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PHILOSOPHICAL VIEW OF MULTICULTURALISM IN MODERN EUROPEAN CINEMATOGRAPHY

**Yulia V. Nikolaeva^{1*}, Svetlana A. Grimalskaya¹,
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Abstract

The article focuses on presenting the importance of the recent changes in the European cinema industry. For the last twenty years we have been witnessing the changes in the process of creating films and in their meaning content. The shift from the classical national cinema (traditional films representing the country in the international arena, with their specific plots, genres, persons, names and means) to lots of films created by descendants from different ethnics and cultures, with their unexpected ideas and solutions their films are based on and that astonish us, as well as the methods used in their implementation. The ideology dominating in the film industry has been changing; this has been confirmed by factors associated with popularity of the new films, their being noticed, marked and appreciated on the top level of the film community, receiving positive reviews, being awarded the prizes in the main European film festivals. It has become imperative to carry out a philosophical analysis of the changes that occurred in the European cinematography. The purpose of article is the philosophical reflection on the issues of the influence of the policy and ideology of multiculturalism on the development of contemporary European cinema. The authors proposed a classification of multicultural processes specific for contemporary European cinematography. Complex analysis makes it possible to more deeply understand how a new discourse has been changing the cinematic space. The polyphony of ideas presented contributes to more adequate cinematic vision of an object and considering it as a global phenomenon. The materials of the article can be used for practical purposes, namely, as auxiliary material in developing general and special university courses on social philosophy, philosophy of culture, culture studies, media studies, and theory of cinema.

Keywords: analysis, multiculturalism, European, ideology, phenomenon

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